

AGING AS A FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND ORGANIZATION OF GERIATRIC MEDICAL CARE.

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Annotation. Currently, people's life expectancy is increasing all over the world. Today, most people can hope to live into their seventies and even longer. In every country in the world, not only the number of elderly people is growing, but also their share in the population. Many factors affect the health status of mature and elderly people. This is a hereditary predisposition to various diseases or vice versa, longevity, and lifestyle and its conditions. Most scientists are sure that a person lives less than the time allotted to him by nature. However, the right attitude to aging, a comfortable psychological state and competent care for the elderly can significantly improve the quality of life of the elderly.

According to WHO, the number of people aged 60 years and older already exceeds the number of children younger than 5 years. In 2030, people aged 60 and older will make up one sixth of the world's inhabitants. By this time, their number will increase from 1 billion in 2020 to 1.4 billion. By 2050 it will double (amounting to 2.1 billion). It is expected that from 2020 to 2050, the number of people aged 80 years and older will triple, and reach 426 million people. According to the State Statistics Committee, as of January 1, 2022, the average life expectancy of the permanent population in Uzbekistan was 73.8 years.

The development of the geriatric care system is impossible without the support of scientific research in the field of gerontology and geriatrics. The special interest that has arisen in our time in the study of age-associated changes in the body is determined not only by the changing demographic situation, but also by the

scientific achievements of recent years in the field of aging biology, primarily in the field of vascular aging and carcinogenesis.

It is in recent years that sufficiently convincing data have been obtained on the possibility of interfering with the biological process of aging, prolonging the period of healthy life, while previously age was considered as an unmodifiable, and therefore not preventable and treatable risk factor.

It is expected that the results of further research will help to understand the key mechanisms of the development of age-related changes and age-associated diseases and, on this basis, to develop the most effective ways of therapeutic effects. Conducting fundamental and applied research aimed at studying the mechanisms of aging will allow us to develop scientifically based methods of preventing the development and progression of senile asthenia, improve the diagnosis and treatment of diseases, optimally plan the volume and nature of medical and social care for the elderly. In addition, the strategy of consistently raising the retirement age, which will inevitably be implemented, will be humane and realistic only if a healthy life is increased with a minimal increase in the period of ill health.

The current demographic situation in our country has required a change in priorities when planning strategies to strengthen the health of the population, namely, a shift in emphasis towards preventive programs.

The purposeful implementation of these programs and the impact on manageable public health risk factors make it possible to make adequate management decisions. These measures will give the maximum effect for the protection of public health, prolongation of active longevity and prevention of age-associated diseases.

To further increase life expectancy, it is necessary to reduce the morbidity and mortality of the older generation, and this is one of the tasks of the geriatric service. Geriatrics is one of the branches of gerontology that deals with the study, prevention and treatment of not only age-associated diseases, but also specific geriatric syndromes. More than 60 geriatric syndromes are known, the most common of

which are senile asthenia, sarcopenia, cognitive impairment, depression, delirium, decreased mobility, falls and fractures, urinary incontinence, sensory deficits. There are a lot of problems associated with age. And all of them have medical, social and economic significance.

It is known that geriatric syndromes not only reduce the quality of life of elderly people, but also increase the risk of dependence on the help of others, hospitalization and death. Most geriatric syndromes remain unrecognized by primary care physicians, which means that measures for their correction and prevention of their progression are not carried out. For example, cognitive impairments common in old age are often diagnosed at the stage of severe dementia, when an elderly person becomes completely dependent on the help of others. A distinctive feature of the geriatric approach is the holistic perception of all the needs of an elderly person — not only medical, but also functional and social.

Despite the obvious achievements in the field of medical care for older citizens, there are a number of problems that need to be solved. The existing organizational structure of medical care for older citizens does not allow organizing the work of the geriatric service as a single system of long-term medical and social care due to the continuity of patient management between different levels of the health system, as well as between health and social protection services. Currently, the availability of geriatric care is insufficient due to the lack of geriatric offices and geriatric departments in polyclinics, as well as geriatric departments in multidisciplinary hospitals.

Poor coordination of actions between health and social protection institutions that provide assistance to older citizens reduces the effectiveness of medical and social assistance. Due to the need to expand medical and social assistance, there is an increasing need to use public-private partnership mechanisms in the provision of medical and social services to older people, to involve the public (volunteers, non-profit structures) in organizing various forms of care for older citizens.

The aging of the population and the development of gerontology and geriatrics require regular updating of educational programs in this specialty in accordance with the current state of the problem, as well as more active training in geriatrics for primary care physicians, nurses, and other specialists working with older citizens. There is also a need for an educational program aimed at attracting the attention of civil society to solving the problems of older people, popularizing the potential and achievements of gerontology and geriatrics, promoting the creation of a friendly infrastructure and psychological atmosphere for older citizens.

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